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Web links to the author's journal account have been redacted from the decision letters as indicated to maintain confidentiality

23rd Mar 22

Dear Dr Meder,

Thank you for submitting your manuscript, "Liquid-solid contact electrification in living plants", to Communications Materials. It has now been seen by 3 referees, whose comments are appended below. You will see that while they find your work of potential interest, they have raised substantial concerns that must be addressed. In light of these comments, we cannot accept the manuscript for publication, but are interested in considering a revised version that addresses these serious concerns.

The reviewers are concerned about the mechanism of charge transfer and ask that this part is elaborated by additional experiments. This point must be convincingly addressed for us to consider your paper further. There are other issues raised by the reviewers which are detailed below in the remarks.

We hope you will find the referees' comments useful as you decide how to proceed. Should further experimental data and analysis allow you to address these criticisms, we would be happy to look at a substantially revised manuscript. However, please bear in mind that we will be reluctant to approach the referees again in the absence of major revisions. If the revision process takes significantly longer than three months, we will be happy to reconsider your paper at a later date, as long as nothing similar has been accepted for publication at Communications Materials or published elsewhere in the meantime.

We are committed to providing a fair and constructive peer-review process. Please don't hesitate to contact us if you wish to discuss the revision in more detail.

When submitting your revised manuscript, please include the following:

-A response letter with a point-by-point reply to each of the referee comments and a description of changes made. Please include the complete referee report in the response letter. Please note that the response letter must be separate to the cover letter to the editors.

-A marked-up version of the manuscript with all changes to the text in a different colored font. Please do not include tracked changes or comments. Please select the file type 'Revised Manuscript - Marked Up' when uploading the manuscript file to our online system.

-A clean version of the manuscript. Please select the file type 'Article File'.

-An updated <https://www.nature.com/documents/nr-editorial-policy-checklist.zip> Editorial Policy checklist, uploaded as a 'Related Manuscript File' type. This checklist is to ensure your paper complies with all relevant editorial policies. If needed, please revise your manuscript in response to these points. Please note that this form is a dynamic 'smart pdf' and must therefore be downloaded and completed in Adobe Reader. Clicking this link will download a zip file containing the pdf.

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We understand that due to the current global situation, the time required for revision may be longer than usual. We would appreciate it if you could keep us informed about an estimated timescale for resubmission, to facilitate our planning. Of course, if you are unable to estimate, we are happy to accommodate necessary extensions nevertheless.

Please do not hesitate to contact me if you have any questions or would like to discuss the required revisions further. Thank you for the opportunity to review your work.

Best regards,

Bilge Baytekin, PhD
Editorial Board Member
Communications Materials
0000-0002-3867-3863

Reviewers' comments:

Reviewer #1 (Remarks to the Author):

In this manuscript, the authors proposed to use leaf-based TENG to harvest rain energy. This is an interesting and promising technology. Yet, the manuscript suffers in several key areas as described in my comments below.

Main comments:

1. The authors believe that this technology can be used for energy harvesting, but the output of a single power-generation unit is far from sufficient to drive microelectronic devices. Therefore, the authors are suggested combining multiple leaves of a plant or multiple plants to form a power-generation array to increase power generation efficiency.
2. What is the specific working mechanism of waxes? The chemical structure of the wax does not supply its strong triboelectrification. As shown in Fig. 6, trichloromethane removes not only the wax but also the micro-nano structures, so it is not possible to determine whether it is these micro-nano structures or the wax itself that affects the output. In addition, most broadleaf plants have wax layers on their surfaces and do not possess superhydrophobic structures; can the output of these plants be similar to that of lotus leaves? Therefore, the authors should design more rigorous experiments to test the conjecture.
3. In Fig.7, the current data are not sufficient to demonstrate that *C. antiquorum* leaves have a similar triboelectrification ability to PTFE. Due to the cumulative nature of triboelectrification, a stable output usually occurs after a period of operation. Therefore, the current signal must be acquired after the output of the device has stabilized. In addition, the current signal is usually not as stable and may be affected by the sampling frequency or the operation method of the instruments. In other TENG-related works, it is more common to measure the amount of transferred charge.

Specific issues:

1. The lines in Fig. 5 are too thin causing the edges of the charts to be unclear.
2. The schematic diagram of the TENG used as a control in Fig. 7 is wrong because the wires are not connected to the bottom electrode.

Reviewer #2 (Remarks to the Author):

The authors study liquid-solid contact electrification in plants with different hydrophobic/hydrophilic properties. Specifically, they show that in plants with more hydrophobic leaves higher current is generated when water droplets impact the leaves. They perform a series of experiments in order to understand this phenomenon. Overall, they present interesting findings well supported by experimental evidence, however they do not elucidate the underlying mechanisms. I understand that this is a complex phenomenon and further studies are required to fully describe it. In any case the setup for harvesting the current during liquid-solid contact electrification is simple consisting only with one electrode inserted in the plant therefore has the potential for environmental energy harvesting but also for biohybrid systems based on plants.

I have some comments that the authors should address prior publication.

1. The authors show a clear dependence of the generated current to the pH of the droplet (Fig.5b). However, they don't provide any explanation for this
2. The authors show that if the water droplets are pre charged the generated current is higher. Can they comment if in nature, rain droplets can be charged under certain circumstances?
3. In page 11, lines 248-257 the authors state: "Removing the epicuticular wax layer considerably reduced the voltage signals generated by deionized water droplets from a current amplitude as high as 2 nA to peaks of -0.1 nA (Fig. 6c). This again suggests that the wax layer plays a major role in signal formation. In fact, impedance spectroscopic analysis of the ion-conductive cellular tissue (Supplementary Fig. 5b) revealed that the tissue resistance is not significantly affected by the chloroform treatment. Similarly, when using pre-charged water, Supplementary Fig. 11 shows that the resulting signals are similar for leaves with and without surface waxes, thus indicating that the general electrostatic induction of charges from the leaf surface into the inner cellular tissue is not affected. This further confirms the crucial role of the waxes in the leaf's water droplet-induced electrical signal"

These statements are contradictory in my opinion. From one side they say that the wax layer is important as the signals are reduced however the impedance does not show any change. I would expect to have a change in the capacitance of the leaf. And then if the "electrostatic induction of charges from the leaf surface into the inner cellular tissue is not affected" with the use of the pre-charged droplets then why the wax layer is important?

4. The authors should give more experimental details on the impedance spectroscopy measurements of the leaves
5. The experimental evidence clearly show that the more hydrophobic leaves result in higher current generation. However, it is not clear why. The authors discuss this in page 12 however they should make the discussion more clear, which phenomena are important for the liquid-solid contact electrification and how hydrophobicity affects them.

Reviewer #3 (Remarks to the Author):

In this manuscript entitled “Liquid-solid contact electrification in living plants”, the authors show how the in-situ micro/nano structures of leaves, the ion concentration and pH, and pre-charging of the droplet influence living plant liquid-solid contact electrification leading to characteristic signals depending on the epicuticular wax layer and the droplet composition. This paper tentatively explores the mechanism of plant-based solid-liquid contact electrification and obtains some interesting experimental results. Considering that some specific issues have not been clearly explained, I recommend the manuscript not be accepted for publication at its present form. Regardless of acceptance, here are some comments for the manuscript which would be useful in improving the manuscript.

1. The two typical species selected in the article (macrorrhiza and esculenta), one is hydrophilic and the other is superhydrophobic, is it because of the difference in the wettability of the material interface that the triboelectricity generated under the same conditions is different? Would you get similar experimental results if you switch to other non-plant-based materials for the two?
2. The influence of different droplet motion states on solid-liquid triboelectricity is huge. The behavior of droplets on the surface interface shown in Figure 2, including collision, bounce, spreading, breaking, etc., has any specific effect on the generation of triboelectricity?
3. Figure 5a explores the influence of ion concentration on the electrical signal. Why does the electrical signal first increase and then decrease, and then increase and then decrease repeatedly with the increase of ion concentration? There should be a clear explanation for this.
4. More concentration gradients should be designed when exploring the effect of different pH on the output in Figure 5b.
5. A phenomenon may be discovered quickly, but its basic understanding takes time. To better explain this plant-based triboelectricity, a charge transfer mechanism diagram should be supplemented.

In summary, the present article does not contain in-depth scientific understanding enough for publication. In this regard, I cannot recommend this article for publication as it is. Instead, I recommend the authors make the experimental design more rigorous and focus on the study of its charge transfer mechanism, revise their manuscript significantly, and resubmit it to the journal if possible.

1 *We thank the reviewers and the editor for their input and the valuable comments that have helped*
2 *us to perform a targeted set of experiments to revise and improve the manuscript. The point-by-*
3 *point responses are given below. We have highlighted the corresponding changes in the revised*
4 *manuscript in yellow.*
5

6
7 **Reviewer 1:**

8
9 In this manuscript, the authors proposed to use leaf-based TENG to harvest rain energy. This is
10 an interesting and promising technology. Yet, the manuscript suffers in several key areas as
11 described in my comments below.

12 *We thank you for this evaluation, for the valuable comments, and your suggestions to help us to*
13 *improve the manuscript.*

14
15 Main comments:

16 1. The authors believe that this technology can be used for energy harvesting, but the output of a
17 single power-generation unit is far from sufficient to drive microelectronic devices. Therefore, the
18 authors are suggested combining multiple leaves of a plant or multiple plants to form a power-
19 generation array to increase power generation efficiency.

20 *We totally agree with you. Although, the power output from a single leaf is not sufficient to directly*
21 *power a device, the main aim of the paper was investigating plant's liquid-solid contact*
22 *electrification related to certain properties of the tissue of living plants. We agree with you that it*
23 *may be possible that connecting multiple leaves, multiple plants, and multiple droplets could lead*
24 *to a sufficient power generation under appropriate conditions to power sensors. Further, targeted*
25 *experiments involving simulating rain with multiple drops occurring on multiple leaves and detailed*
26 *outdoor tests are planned to assess these aspects. Also taking into account the higher kinetic*
27 *energy of the raindrops, their potential surface charge, and the impingement of multiple droplets*
28 *on a single leaf we are optimistic to power small devices. Yet, the current article is focussing on*
29 *the origin of the signals generated.*

30 *We streamlined the text accordingly to clarify the scope of the article and added discussion on*
31 *potential for energy harvesting.*

32 *Abstract:*

33 “Contact electrification has gained increasing interest as mechanism that generates charges
34 on most surfaces. It has been shown that also plant leaves generate electrification by both
35 solid-solid and liquid-solid contact. Yet, it is unclear, how a common event like water droplets
36 hitting the leaf surface charges it, creates electrical signals in the tissue, and which structural
37 features affect this phenomenon.”

38 *Introduction:*

39 “[...] therefore, the diverse materials found in plants can result in different charging patterns
40 and more information is needed on how contact charging occurs in nature. How liquid-
41 contact electrification arises on the hierarchical, in-situ leaf surface of living plants remains

42 unclear and how properties like superhydrophobicity, surface wax layers, and droplet
43 properties at the water-leaf interface enhance the phenomenon or reduce it.”

44 *Discussion:*

45 “The signals related to single rain drop impingements lead to voltage and current peaks of up
46 to $\sim 0.2 \pm 0.02$ V and $\sim 2 \pm 0.2$ nA corresponding to ~ 0.4 nW peak power while the current peak
47 duration is about 60 ms at FWHM. These values suggest suitability for, e.g., sensing rain. 59
48 Moreover, if signals from multiple droplets add up, also energy harvesting may be
49 considered, possibly by combining the output of multiple leaves and plants which will be part
50 of a dedicated future study.”

51 *Conclusions:*

52 “When droplets are uncharged and at low ion concentration, contact electrification causes
53 the signals and they are larger on densely wax-coated superhydrophobic plants. Yet,
54 hydrophobicity alone does not enhance signals. Pre-charged droplets, as they may occur in
55 nature, lead to even higher signals compared to those obtained from contact electrification.
56 The results provide a base for further understanding the origin of liquid-solid contact
57 electrification signals in living organisms like plants, but also as inspiration for bioinspired
58 artificial, or biohybrid energy harvesters and sensors.”

59
60 2. What is the specific working mechanism of waxes? The chemical structure of the wax does not
61 supply its strong triboelectrification. As shown in Fig. 6, trichloromethane removes not only the
62 wax but also the micro-nano structures, so it is not possible to determine whether it is these micro-
63 nano structures or the wax itself that affects the output. In addition, most broadleaf plants have
64 wax layers on their surfaces and do not possess superhydrophobic structures; can the output of
65 these plants be similar to that of lotus leaves? Therefore, the authors should design more rigorous
66 experiments to test the conjecture.

67 *Thank you for this important comment, we totally agree and performed a targeted set of*
68 *experiments to investigate and better address these points.*

69 *We now tested liquid-solid contact electrification before and after the epicuticular waxes on the*
70 *leaf surface have been either removed or carefully heated for short periods which only*
71 *melted/changed the nanostructure but did not remove the wax layer (no chemical changes*
72 *assumed). The new Figure 6 and new Movie 3 show the effect on the droplet interaction. The*
73 *results demonstrate that the signals after melting the nanostructures only slightly reduced*
74 *compared to the pristine surface (other than during the trichloromethane treatment where they*
75 *strongly decrease). This implies, that the nanostructure indeed plays a role as also assumed by*
76 *Kim et al. (Adv. Mater. 2018, 1804949. <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.201804949>) for plant leaf’s*
77 *solid-solid contact electrification, hence both, chemical nature and structure of the waxes*
78 *contribute. According changes can be found below.*

79 *The second set of experiments to address your question was expanding the range of non-*
80 *superhydrophobic plants tested. We compared now three superhydrophobic plants (C.*
81 *antiquorum, N. nucifera, and T. majus) and three non-superhydrophobic plants (A. macrorrhiza,*
82 *H. helix, and N. oleander) in terms of surface structures, droplet interaction, and electrical signals*

83 (new Fig.7 and new Movie 4). The results clearly show that the superhydrophobic plants cause
84 higher electrical signals upon droplet contact likely due to their higher density of surface waxes.
85 We also show that hydrophobicity alone does not generate higher signals as plants treated with
86 trichloromethane or after wax melting still showed relatively high contact angles and droplet
87 interactions similar to the pristine, superhydrophobic surface (see Figure 6 and Movie 3). Thus,
88 we assume that a combination of nanostructure, chemistry, density of waxes, and possible water
89 films remaining on the surface of hydrophilic leaves all affect the signals. These factors necessarily
90 depend on the species and the conditions it grows in.

91 The following changes have been made in the revised version.

92 *Results:*

93 "A specific experiment was then designed to investigate the influence of epicuticular waxes
94 on the electrical signals generated by *C. antiquorum*. Therefore, the electrical signals of an
95 untreated leaf were compared with those of the same leaf after 1) gentle melting of the waxes
96 nanostructure resulting in a flatter epicuticular wax layer and 2) removal of the epicuticular
97 waxes through a chloroform treatment. SEM images in Fig. 6a clearly confirm the successful
98 melting and removal of the epicuticular waxes and show that the epidermis and papillae
99 remained after treatment. Digital microscopy images using reflected light further suggest the
100 melted wax layer by showing a shinier leaf surface (Supplementary Fig. S11). FTIR
101 measurements (Supplementary Fig. S12) before and after wax removal confirmed a
102 reduction of the vibrations at 1460 cm^{-1} , 1470 cm^{-1} , and 719 cm^{-1} which correspond to
103 structures present in the cutin and the waxes.⁴³ Moreover, both, the epicuticular wax melting
104 or removal caused a reduction of the contact angle by $\sim 30^\circ$ (Fig. 6c) compared to the pristine
105 leaf. Yet, the contact angle remains high at $\sim 120^\circ$ and the droplet interaction with the treated
106 leaf surfaces was still hydrophobic and not comparable with that of the hydrophilic *A.*
107 *macrorrhiza* leaf (Supplementary Movie 3).

108 Both treatments have a clear effect on the electrical signals generated by the leaf's liquid-
109 solid contact electrification (Fig. 6b). Removing the epicuticular wax layer strongly reduces
110 the generated voltage signals caused by deionized water droplets from a current amplitude
111 of about 1 nA to peaks of -0.1 nA. Melting the waxes and changing the nanostructure to a
112 flatter epicuticular wax layer also reduce the signals about twice in magnitude to an average
113 amplitude of ~ 0.5 nA. More detailed voltage, charge, and current data of single droplets of
114 the experiment summarized in Fig. 6b can be found in Supplementary Fig. S13. The results
115 clearly suggest that the wax layer plays a major role in the signal formation, whereas

116 removing the waxes affects the signals stronger than its structural changes. It is also clear
 117 that although the treated leaves remained hydrophobic with contact angles of $\sim 120^\circ$, the
 118 signals reduced and hydrophobicity alone may not play the main role in signal formation. To
 119 assure that the variation in the signals is indeed due to the variation in the surface waxes, we
 120 confirmed that the treatments have only a marginal influence on the cellular tissue acting as
 121 electrode. Additionally, the impedance spectroscopy already given in Supplementary Fig. S7c
 122 reveals that the tissue impedance varies in the same order of magnitude and is not
 123 significantly affected by both treatments, excluding a major impact on the signal magnitude.”

124

125 **Fig. 6.** Influence of nanostructure and selective removal of epicuticular waxes on the water-
 126 droplet contact electrification of *C. antiquorum*. a) Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) of a
 127 *C. antiquorum* leaf when pristine (left), epicuticular waxes are gently melted (center) and
 128 when the waxes are removed (right). b) Comparison of electric signals on a *C. antiquorum*
 129 leaf with intact waxes, molten wax, and removed waxes, respectively. The boxplot
 130 summarizes median (center line), 75th and 25th percentile (box), and maximum and
 131 minimum corresponding to 1.5 times the interquartile range (whiskers), and possible
 132 outliers (diamonds) of measurements from 50 droplets for the pristine and molten leaf (and
 133 20 droplets after wax removal). Time-resolved signals for current, charge, and voltage are
 134 given in Supplementary Fig. S12. The schematics on top of the graph illustrate the different
 135 morphology of the waxes in the three cases reported: intact wax crystals in the pristine leaf,
 136 molten waxes forming a flatter, continuous layer, and complete absence of epicuticular
 137 waxes. c) Effect of the wax melting and wax removal on the water contact angle (N=5) of a
 138 *C. antiquorum* leaf.

139

140

141 **Figure S13.** Current, charge, and voltage signals recorded for *C. antiquorum* of pristine
142 leaves, after changing the nanostructure of the epicuticular waxes by melting and after wax
143 removal by chloroform. Experiments were performed with DI water.

144
145

146
147 **Figure S6.** Impedance spectroscopy of the plant tissue. [...]. b) Impedance between stem and
148 lamina of *C. antiquorum* of leaf before and after melting the waxes . c) Impedance between
149 stem and lamina of *C. antiquorum* of leaf before and after removing the waxes through a CHCl_3
150 treatment.

151

152 [...]

153 “Subsequently, we compared the behavior of further plant species: three superhydrophobic
154 species (*Colocasia antiquorum*, *Nelumbo nucifera* and *Tropaeolum majus*) and three non-
155 hydrophobic species (*Alocasia macrorrhiza*, *Hedera helix* and *Nerium oleander*). Images of
156 surface structures and contact angles of all species can be found in Supplementary Fig. S14

157 and recording of the leaf-droplet interactions in Movie 4). The results in Fig. 7 confirm that
 158 superhydrophobic species in general produced higher current amplitudes than hydrophilic
 159 species during droplet interaction while less significant variations among the
 160 superhydrophobic or hydrophilic species, respectively occurred. Yet, due to the previous
 161 analysis on leaves with varied wax structure, the clear trend that superhydrophobic plants
 162 have higher signals than hydrophilic plants may not solely be caused by the
 163 hydrophobic/hydrophilic properties, but by parameters of the wax layer such as
 164 micro/nanostructure, wax density, and chemistry.”

165

a.

166

167 **Fig. 7.** Comparison of water droplet contact electrification on different plant species: fresh
168 leaves of *N. nucifera*, *T. majus*, *C. antiquorum*, *H. helix*, *N. oleander* and *A. macrorrhiza*. Leaf-
169 droplet interactions can be seen in Movies 2 and 3. The boxplot summarizes median
170 (center line), 75th and 25th percentile (box), and maximum and minimum corresponding to
171 1.5 times the interquartile range (whiskers), and possible outliers (diamonds) of
172 measurements from 50 droplets (except for *T. majus*, 20 droplets). The measurements have
173 been performed after initially 3000 droplets have been dropped on the leaves. Leaf
174 photographs and contact angle for each species are given.

175

176

177

178

179 **Figure S15.** Electric signals of liquid-solid contact electrification of artificial materials. a)
180 Boxplot comparing the current signals produced by PET, silicone rubber, PTFE and FEP. The
181 boxplot summarizes median (center line), 75th and 25th percentile (box), and maximum and
182 minimum corresponding to 1.5 times the interquartile range (whiskers), and possible
183 outliers (diamonds) of measurements from 50 droplets. The measurements have been
184 performed after initially 3000 droplets have been dropped on the leaves. b) Structure of the
185 four artificial systems for measuring liquid-solid contact electrification on the top surface. c)

186 Current, charge and voltage amplitudes as function of number of droplets (data points and
187 error bars represent mean and average of 50 droplets each).

188

189 *Discussion:*

190 “When droplets are uncharged, cuticle contact electrification is significant cause of the
191 electrical signal measured. Our results clearly show which factors of the leaf lead to higher
192 or lower contact electrification upon droplet interaction. The effects are often deeply
193 interconnected and mechanisms overlay on highly complex surfaces of the leaves. Yet, our
194 results point to the following behavior.

195 First, clearly, the epicuticular wax layer plays an essential role. The two features especially
196 affecting leaf’s liquid contact electrification are a) its nanostructure and b) its specific
197 chemistry. The latter was anticipated for solid-solid contact electrification of leaves found by
198 Kim et al. ³³ Our results suggest that the wax presence and chemistry may play a more
199 important role compared to its micro-/nanostructure as melting the waxes to achieve a
200 flatter surface reduced the signals only about twice in *C. antiquorum*. However, removing the
201 epicuticular waxes from the leaf reduced the signals tenfold. Moreover, the signals after wax-
202 removal are reaching similar current, voltage and charge magnitudes to those obtained from
203 plants that do not have a similarly dense wax layer. This suggests that the removal has clearly
204 a more significant effect than just morphological changes in the wax layer.

205 Second, another important aspect is the superhydrophobicity. Results of the tests performed
206 on the three superhydrophobic species showed that they generate higher signals compared
207 with those obtained from the three tested hydrophilic species. However,
208 superhydrophobicity/hydrophobicity alone is not sufficient to guarantee high (here, ~1-2 nA)
209 leaf-droplet contact electrification signals: experiments with removed wax layers in *C.*
210 *antiquorum* still showed hydrophobic behavior (contact angles 120°), but signals were low
211 and similar to hydrophilic plants. This again shows that the presence of a dense,
212 nanostructured wax layer is more important than hydrophobicity, although these two
213 properties are often connected in natural conditions. However, there is another crucial
214 feature of superhydrophobic surfaces, which is their ability for self-cleaning and complete

215 removal of water from the surface. On hydrophilic plants, instead, water layers remain and
216 may partially screen charges affecting signal formation and induction.^{8,9,16,44-46}. Indeed, the
217 contact time of the water droplet, the bouncing-off rates, and the remaining water films also
218 play a role in liquid-solid contact electrification⁴⁷⁻⁴⁹. Moreover, although the droplet
219 spreading area on the hydrophilic *A. macrorrhiza* and the superhydrophobic *C. antiquorum*
220 was similar, it is expected that the water-surface contact area is higher on the hydrophilic
221 leaf surface especially on the micro-/nanoscale^{50,51}. Increasing contact area is usually
222 associated with higher leaf contact electrification and related signals^{3,52}. There may be
223 several reasons why this was not observed in our case, for example the remaining water
224 layers screening charges as mentioned above or the fact that efficient contact with few points
225 on the surface is already sufficient to create high contact charges (one fundamental charge
226 in about 100'000 surface atoms ($\sim 1000 \text{ nm}^2$) can yield thousands of volts as highlighted by
227 Lacks et al.⁵³). Here, again, the wax layers nanostructure with multiple sharp edges which
228 are transiently contacted by the droplet could provide such points/hot spots.”

229
230 3. In Fig.7, the current data are not sufficient to demonstrate that *C. antiquorum* leaves have a
231 similar triboelectrification ability to PTFE. Due to the cumulative nature of triboelectrification, a
232 stable output usually occurs after a period of operation. Therefore, the current signal must be
233 acquired after the output of the device has stabilized. In addition, the current signal is usually not
234 as stable and may be affected by the sampling frequency or the operation method of the
235 instruments. In other TENG-related works, it is more common to measure the amount of
236 transferred charge.

237 *Thank you for pointing that out. We changed our experimental setup in a manner that we can*
238 *perform tests with over several thousand droplets to observe variation of the signals with higher*
239 *droplet numbers. We measured signals of all plants and artificial materials for up to 5000 droplets*
240 *showing for some species a clear initial increase and with a stabilization of the signals after*
241 *maximal 3000 droplets. For other samples, especially *C. antiquorum*, the signals did not increase*
242 *significantly and remained stable. We thus compare all data after 3000 droplets have impacted*
243 *the samples.*

244 *Moreover, we typically always recorded current, charge, and voltage signals for each sample*
245 *(shown for example in the Supporting Information in Figures 8 and 15. We observed that with the*
246 *current signals, we clearly achieved the highest resolution and their trend totally agree with charge*
247 *and voltage signals. Especially, for plant surfaces producing very low charging, current signals*
248 *could still be observed due to the capability of the electrometer to analyse signals down to the pA*
249 *range whereas it was not always possible to records a clean voltage or charge signals due to the*

250 lower detection limit. In addition, we recorded all data at a very high sampling frequency of 20 kHz
251 which provided sufficient resolution to resolve the current spikes.

252 The following changes have been made in the revised version:

253

254 *Materials and methods:*

255 “The current (nA), charge (nC) and voltage (V) signals obtained from typically 20-60 droplets
256 were recorded in a resolution of 20,000 datapoints per second. To assure that the signal of a
257 sample stabilized at its maximum, we recorded how the signal develops over up to 5000
258 droplets, showing that after 3000 droplets the signals typically stabilized. Several samples
259 (especially in *C. antiquorum* and *A. macrorrhiza*) showed stable signals over the whole range.
260 Thus, to compare data between different samples, measurements were performed after 3000
261 droplets have impacted the surface.”

262 *Results:*

263 “Moreover, we observed how the signals evolve with higher droplet numbers using up to
264 3500 droplets (Supplementary Fig. S5). We observed that the signals for both plants are
265 extremely stable (e.g., for some artificial materials, a signal stabilization occurred at over
266 3000 droplets).”

267 [...]

268 “Moreover, we compared the electrical signals generated by artificial materials upon droplet
269 interaction tested under the same conditions. Supplementary Fig. S15a shows an analysis of
270 polyethylene terephthalate (PET), silicone rubber, fluorinated ethylene propylene, (FEP),
271 and polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) applied on a flexible indium-tin oxide (ITO) electrode.
272 As expected, different amplitudes are achieved for the different material surfaces due to the
273 expected material-dependency of liquid-solid contact electrification. Interestingly, although
274 all artificial materials generated higher amplitudes than *C. antiquorum*, the current, voltage,
275 and charge signals generated by this plant were still found within the same magnitude of
276 those of, e.g., highly fluorinated artificial materials like PTFE.”

277

278 *Supporting information:*

279

280 **Figure S5.** Electrical signals as function of droplet number contacting the *C. antiquorum*

281 (first column) and *A. macrorrhiza* (second column) leaves. a) current, b) charge, and c)

282 voltage signals, respectively recorded on pristine leaves. Each datapoint represents 50

283 droplets.

285

286 **Figure S15.** Electric signals of liquid-solid contact electrification of artificial materials. a)

287 Boxplot comparing the current signals produced by PET, silicone rubber, PTFE and FEP. The

288 boxplot summarizes median (center line), 75th and 25th percentile (box), and maximum and

289 minimum corresponding to 1.5 times the interquartile range (whiskers), and possible

290 outliers (diamonds) of measurements from 50 droplets. The measurements have been

291 performed after initially 3000 droplets have been dropped on the leaves. b) Structure of the

292 four artificial systems for measuring liquid-solid contact electrification on the top surface. c)

293 Current, charge and voltage amplitudes as function of number of droplets (data points and

294 error bars represent mean and average of 50 droplets each).

295

296 Specific issues:

- 297 1. The lines in Fig. 5 are too thin causing the edges of the charts to be unclear.
- 298 2. The schematic diagram of the TENG used as a control in Fig. 7 is wrong because the wires are not connected to the bottom electrode.

300 *We thank you for spotting this out and corrected it accordingly. The part of Fig. 7 addressed is*
301 *now Supplementary Fig. S15 (reported above).*

302

303

304

305 *Thank you again for the comments that have greatly helped us to improve the manuscript.*

306

307

308

309 **Reviewer 2:**

310

311 The authors study liquid-solid contact electrification in plants with different hydrophobic/hydrophilic
312 properties. Specifically, they show that in plants with more hydrophobic leaves higher current is
313 generated when water droplets impact the leaves. They perform a series of experiments in order
314 to understand this phenomenon. Overall, they present interesting findings well supported by
315 experimental evidence, however they do not elucidate the underlying mechanisms. I understand
316 that this is a complex phenomenon and further studies are required to fully describe it. In any case
317 the setup for harvesting the current during liquid-solid contact electrification is simple consisting
318 only with one electrode inserted in the plant therefore has the potential for environmental energy
319 harvesting but also for biohybrid systems based on plants.

320 I have some comments that the authors should address prior publication.

321

322 *We thank you for this evaluation, for all comments, and your suggestions which helped us to*
323 *improve the manuscript. We also performed a targeted set of experiments to further elucidate the*
324 *mechanism.*
325

326 1. The authors show a clear dependence of the generated current to the pH of the droplet (Fig.5b).
327 However, they don't provide any explanation for this

328 *We thank you for the suggestion and extended the discussion on the effect of the pH on the*
329 *generated signals as follows.*

330 *Discussion:*

331 "Our results also show that the pH affects the signals amplitude. Whereas basic pH did not
332 have a significant effect, at pH 3 (corresponding to an HCl concentration of 1mM) signals
333 significantly reduced. The pH expectedly has an influence on the liquid-solid contact
334 electrification^{44,55}. However, on leaves this is more complex. It was shown that exposure to
335 pH 3 can significantly damage the epicuticular wax layer leading to a melted appearance as
336 reported in ⁵⁷. Thus, as we showed the strong effect of the wax layer on the signals when
337 melting or removing the waxes, the signal reduction at low pH can be due to the damage of
338 the wax layer. Yet, also in regards of occurrence of acidic rain in natural environments, a
339 dedicated study of the complex effect of the pH in future would be interesting. "

340

341

342 2. The authors show that if the water droplets are pre charged the generated current is higher.
343 Can they comment if in nature, rain droplets can be charged under certain circumstances?

344 *We thank you for this comment. There are indeed several works that indicate that raindrops charge*
345 *in clouds and while falling (Gunn (1955): Droplet-electrification processes and coagulation in*
346 *stable and unstable clouds, journal of atmospheric sciences, 12(6), 511-518.; Twomey (1956):*
347 *The electrification of individual cloud droplets, Tellus, 8:4; Wang (2021), Study of Contact*
348 *Electrification at Liquid-Gas Interface, ACS Nano, 15 (11)). Thus, it is expectable that this will have*
349 *effects on the signals in outdoor conditions when droplet charging occurs.*

350 *We added this information in the discussion of our experiments with pre-charged water droplets.*

351 *Discussion:*

352 "However, under outdoor conditions a frequent phenomenon could be particularly beneficial
353 and interesting to evaluate. Water droplets may charge⁶⁰ due to diffusion of atmospheric
354 ions⁶¹ and especially droplets in thunderstorms, are accompanied by formation of electric
355 fields due to charge separation⁶² Moreover, the friction with the surrounding air produces
356 charges on the surface of droplets.⁶³ We indeed showed that pre-charged droplets generate
357 higher signals largely independent of the plant species and charges on the droplets are
358 induced into the tissue where they can be harvested."

359

360 3. In page 11, lines 248-257 the authors state: "Removing the epicuticular wax layer considerably
361 reduced the voltage signals generated by deionized water droplets from a current amplitude as
362 high as 2 nA to peaks of -0.1 nA (Fig. 6c). This again suggests that the wax layer plays a major

363 role in signal formation. In fact, impedance spectroscopic analysis of the ion-conductive cellular
364 tissue (Supplementary Fig. 5b) revealed that the tissue resistance is not significantly affected by
365 the chloroform treatment. Similarly, when using pre-charged water, Supplementary Fig. 11 shows
366 that the resulting signals are similar for leaves with and without surface waxes, thus indicating that
367 the general electrostatic induction of charges from the leaf surface into the inner cellular tissue is
368 not affected. This further confirms the crucial role of the waxes in the leaf's water droplet-induced
369 electrical signal"

370 These statements are contradictory in my opinion. From one side they say that the wax layer is
371 important as the signals are reduced however the impedance does not show any change. I would
372 expect to have a change in the capacitance of the leaf. And then if the "electrostatic induction of
373 charges from the leaf surface into the inner cellular tissue is not affected" with the use of the pre-
374 charged droplets then why the wax layer is important?

375 *Thank you for spotting out that these points have not been clear. The aim of the impedance*
376 *spectroscopy was to examine if the wax removal treatment would affect the impedance of the*
377 *inner tissue acting as electrode in our experiments. We thus inserted one electrode in the stem*
378 *tissue and one in the leaf tissue. It demonstrated that both treatments, either wax melting or wax*
379 *removal by chloroform did not affect the tissue impedance. The experiment with the pre-charged*
380 *droplets showed that the charge from the leaf surface is still transferred (induced) into the inner*
381 *tissue so that we can assume that during experiments with uncharged droplets, we indeed*
382 *observed an effect of the wax-related contact charging. We now performed also further tests to*
383 *elucidate the role of the waxes as reported in the replies to your comment number 5.*

384 *The following changes were made in the revised version:*

385 *Results:*

386 "To assure that the variation in the signals is indeed due to the variation in the surface waxes,
387 we confirmed that the treatments have only a marginal influence on the cellular tissue acting
388 as electrode. Additionally, the impedance spectroscopy already given in Supplementary Fig.
389 S7c reveals that the tissue impedance varies in the same order of magnitude and is not
390 significantly affected by both treatments, excluding a major impact on the signal magnitude."

391
392 4. The authors should give more experimental details on the impedance spectroscopy
393 measurements of the leaves

394 *We thank you for pointing that out and have added the following:*

395 *Materials and Methods:*

396 "Impedance spectroscopy was performed using an E4980A Precision LCR Meter (Keysight
397 Technologies, USA). Two gold-coated pin electrodes were inserted in the plant tissue, one in
398 the leaf tissue and one in the stem tissue. The position of the electrode in the stem to measure
399 at different distances. The electrodes were penetrating the cuticle and contacting the inner

400 ion-conductive cellular tissue. The complex impedance was measured at indicated
401 frequencies (between 0.1kHz to 1MHz) applying a 1V bias.”

402
403 5. The experimental evidence clearly show that the more hydrophobic leaves result in higher
404 current generation. However, it is not clear why. The authors discuss this in page 12 however they
405 should make the discussion more clear, which phenomena are important for the liquid-solid
406 contact electrification and how hydrophobicity affects them.

407 *We thank you for this comment and performed a new set of experiments to better elucidate the*
408 *mechanisms. We restructured the discussion and put more emphasis on describing which*
409 *phenomena affect the signals.*

410 *New set of experiments:*

411 *We performed experiments elucidate the effect of the wax nanostructure. For this, we measured*
412 *the electrical signals before and after the waxes on the leaf surface have been carefully melted by*
413 *gentle heat treatments for short periods. This modified only the nanostructure to a flatter layer but*
414 *did not remove the wax layer so that we could assume that the chemical structure remains similar*
415 *but only the nanostructure changes. The results show that the signals only slightly reduced*
416 *compared to the pristine surface (other than during the trichloromethane treatment where they*
417 *strongly decrease). This implies, that the nanostructure indeed plays a role but key contribution*
418 *has the chemical nature of the waxes. This is also a known effect in contact electrification of*
419 *artificial materials and the enhancement of electric fields at nanostructures compared to flat*
420 *surfaces.*

421 *Moreover, we extended the range of plants tested comparing now three superhydrophobic plants*
422 *(C. antiquorum, N. nucifera and T. majus) and three non-superhydrophobic plants (A.*
423 *macrorrhiza, H. helix and N. oleander) in terms of surface structures and electrical signals. In*
424 *addition, we tracked in detail the signal generation and droplet contact and spreading in*
425 *millisecond resolution to better understand at which moment the signals during droplet-leaf*
426 *interaction are generated.*

427

428 **Fig. 6.** Influence of nanostructure and selective removal of epicuticular waxes on the water-
 429 droplet contact electrification of *C. antiquorum*. a) Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) of a
 430 *C. antiquorum* leaf when pristine (left), epicuticular waxes are gently melted (center) and
 431 when the waxes are removed (right). b) Comparison of electric signals on a *C. antiquorum*
 432 leaf with intact waxes, molten wax, and removed waxes, respectively. The boxplot
 433 summarizes median (center line), 75th and 25th percentile (box), and maximum and
 434 minimum corresponding to 1.5 times the interquartile range (whiskers), and possible
 435 outliers (diamonds) of measurements from 50 droplets for the pristine and molten leaf (and
 436 20 droplets after wax removal). Time-resolved signals for current, charge, and voltage are

437 given in Supplementary Fig. S12. The schematics on top of the graph illustrate the different
438 morphology of the waxes in the three cases reported: intact wax crystals in the pristine leaf,
439 molten waxes forming a flatter, continuous layer, and complete absence of epicuticular
440 waxes. c) Effect of the wax melting and wax removal on the water contact angle (N=5) of a
441 *C. antiquorum* leaf.

442

443

444

445 **Figure S13.** Current, charge, and voltage signals recorded for *C. antiquorum* of pristine
446 leaves, after changing the nanostructure of the epicuticular waxes by melting and after wax
447 removal by chloroform. Experiments were performed with DI water.

448

449 **Fig. 7.** Comparison of water droplet contact electrification on different plant species: fresh
450 leaves of *N. nucifera*, *T. majus*, *C. antiquorum*, *H. helix*, *N. oleander* and *A. macrorrhiza*. Leaf-
451 droplet interactions can be seen in Movies 2 and 3. The boxplot summarizes median
452 (center line), 75th and 25th percentile (box), and maximum and minimum corresponding to
453 1.5 times the interquartile range (whiskers), and possible outliers (diamonds) of
454 measurements from 50 droplets (except for *T. majus*, 20 droplets). The measurements have
455 been performed after initially 3000 droplets have been dropped on the leaves. Leaf
456 photographs and contact angle for each species are given.

457

458

459 *Discussion:*

460 “Our results clearly confirm that living plant leaves are a platform that generates electrical
461 signals upon contact with water droplets, either through contact electrification on the outer
462 leaf or through pre-charged droplets landing on the leaf. In both cases, the charges received
463 by the external leaf surface are electrostatically induced in the ion-conductive tissue.

464 When droplets are uncharged, cuticle contact electrification is significant cause of the
465 electrical signal measured. Our results clearly show which factors of the leaf lead to higher
466 or lower contact electrification upon droplet interaction. The effects are often deeply
467 interconnected and mechanisms overlay on highly complex surfaces of the leaves. Yet, our
468 results point to the following behavior.

469 First, clearly, the epicuticular wax layer plays an essential role. The two features especially
470 affecting leaf’s liquid contact electrification are a) its nanostructure and b) its specific
471 chemistry. The latter was anticipated for solid-solid contact electrification of leaves found by
472 Kim et al. ³³ Our results suggest that the wax presence and chemistry may play a more
473 important role compared to its micro-/nanostructure as melting the waxes to achieve a
474 flatter surface reduced the signals only about twice in *C. antiquorum*. However, removing the
475 epicuticular waxes from the leaf reduced the signals tenfold. Moreover, the signals after wax-
476 removal are reaching similar current, voltage and charge magnitudes to those obtained from
477 plants that do not have a similarly dense wax layer. This suggests that the removal has clearly
478 a more significant effect than just morphological changes in the wax layer.

479 Second, another important aspect is the superhydrophobicity. Results of the tests performed

480 on the three superhydrophobic species showed that they generate higher signals compared
481 with those obtained from the three tested hydrophilic species. However,
482 superhydrophobicity/hydrophobicity alone is not sufficient to guarantee high (here, ~1-2 nA)
483 leaf-droplet contact electrification signals: experiments with removed wax layers in *C.*
484 *antiquorum* still showed hydrophobic behavior (contact angles 120°), but signals were low
485 and similar to hydrophilic plants. This again shows that the presence of a dense,
486 nanostructured wax layer is more important than hydrophobicity, although these two
487 properties are often connected in natural conditions. However, there is another crucial
488 feature of superhydrophobic surfaces, which is their ability for self-cleaning and complete
489 removal of water from the surface. On hydrophilic plants, instead, water layers remain and
490 may partially screen charges affecting signal formation and induction.^{8,9,16,44-46}. Indeed, the
491 contact time of the water droplet, the bouncing-off rates, and the remaining water films also
492 play a role in liquid-solid contact electrification⁴⁷⁻⁴⁹. Moreover, although the droplet
493 spreading area on the hydrophilic *A. macrorrhiza* and the superhydrophobic *C. antiquorum*
494 was similar, it is expected that the water-surface contact area is higher on the hydrophilic
495 leaf surface especially on the micro-/nanoscale^{50,51}. Increasing contact area is usually
496 associated with higher leaf contact electrification and related signals^{3,52}. There may be
497 several reasons why this was not observed in our case, for example the remaining water
498 layers screening charges as mentioned above or the fact that efficient contact with few points
499 on the surface is already sufficient to create high contact charges (one fundamental charge
500 in about 100'000 surface atoms (~1000 nm²) can yield thousands of volts as highlighted by
501 Lacks et al.⁵³). Here, again, the wax layers nanostructure with multiple sharp edges which
502 are transiently contacted by the droplet could provide such points/hot spots.

503 Next, to the leaf properties, also the properties of the droplet played an essential role in the
504 leaf liquid-solid contact electrification. The role of pre-charged droplets, as occurring for
505 example in thunderstorms is discussed later. The signals generated by uncharged water
506 droplets on *C. antiquorum* leaves were strongly affected by the ion strengths and the pH
507 following thereby trends also reported for artificial materials^{22,54,55}. Ion-rich solutions
508 typically cause charge reduction by screening effects.^{55,56}. The previous increase with the
509 ion concentration that we observed in the *C. antiquorum* leaves below 1mM, seemed to be
510 beneficial, e.g., an increasing droplet conductivity compared to deionized water as suggested

511 in ⁵⁵. Whereas then higher molarities caused a progressive decrease of the signals probably
512 due to charge screening. Thus, superimposing effects may occur that do not always show a
513 linear behavior and would need deeper investigation especially on complex leaf surfaces.
514 Our results also show that the pH affects the signals amplitude. Whereas basic pH did not
515 have a significant effect, at pH 3 (corresponding to an HCl concentration of 1mM) signals
516 significantly reduced. The pH expectedly has an influence on the liquid-solid contact
517 electrification^{44,55}. However, the effect of pH on leaves is more complex to determine. It was
518 shown that exposure to pH 3 can significantly damage the epicuticular wax layer leading to
519 a melted appearance as reported in ⁵⁷. Thus, as we showed the strong effect of the wax layer
520 on the signals when melting or removing the waxes, the signal reduction at low pH can be
521 due to the damage of the wax layer. Yet, also in regards of occurrence of acidic rain in natural
522 environments, a dedicated study of the complex effect of the pH in future would be
523 interesting. “

524

525 *Thank you again for the comments that have helped us to improve the manuscript.*

526

527

528 **Reviewer 3:**

529 In this manuscript entitled “Liquid-solid contact electrification in living plants”, the authors show
530 how the in-situ micro/nano structures of leaves, the ion concentration and pH, and pre-charging
531 of the droplet influence living plant liquid-solid contact electrification leading to characteristic
532 signals depending on the epicuticular wax layer and the droplet composition. This paper tentatively
533 explores the mechanism of plant-based solid-liquid contact electrification and obtains some
534 interesting experimental results. Considering that some specific issues have not been clearly
535 explained, I recommend the manuscript not be accepted for publication at its present form.
536 Regardless of acceptance, here are some comments for the manuscript which would be useful in
537 improving the manuscript.

538

539 *We thank you for this evaluation, for the valuable comments and your suggestions to help us to*
540 *improve the manuscript.*

541

542 1. The two typical species selected in the article (macrorrhiza and esculenta), one is hydrophilic
543 and the other is superhydrophobic, is it because of the difference in the wettability of the material
544 interface that the triboelectricity generated under the same conditions is different? Would you get
545 similar experimental results if you switch to other non-plant-based materials for the two?

546 *Thank you for these questions and the hint to better clarify these points in the revised article. We*
547 *performed an additional set of experiments to better analyze and distinguish the role of the surface*
548 *waxes, their nanostructure, and the leaf's hydrophobic behaviour. These results showed different*
549 *features of the leaf surface play all a role in signal generation, the waxes (in terms of chemical*
550 *nature, surface density, and nanostructure) are a key for the leaf's liquid-solid contact*
551 *electrification. At the same time the results suggest that the hydrophobicity plays a rather*
552 *secondary role. We modified the epicuticular waxes from *C. antiquorum* by removal or by melting*
553 *to change their nanostructure without removing the layer. The contact angle remains still high after*
554 *treatment (~120°) and the *C. antiquorum* leaf still shows a rather hydrophobic surface. However,*
555 *the signals by contact electrification decreased significantly: melting reduced the signals twice and*
556 *epicuticular wax removal tenfold. This suggests that the hydrophobicity is less important compared*
557 *to the wax chemical nature and nanostructure for the generation of the electrical signals. Yet other*
558 *aspects, like water interaction time, contact area, remaining water layers may influence the signal*
559 *generation comparing between superhydrophobic and hydrophilic plants. We extended our*
560 *analysis moreover to other plant species and more artificial materials. We added the results and*
561 *revised the discussion accordingly.*

562

563

564 **Fig. 6.** Influence of nanostructure and selective removal of epicuticular waxes on the water-
 565 droplet contact electrification of *C. antiquorum*. a) Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) of a
 566 *C. antiquorum* leaf when pristine (left), epicuticular waxes are gently melted (center) and
 567 when the waxes are removed (right). b) Comparison of electric signals on a *C. antiquorum*
 568 leaf with intact waxes, molten wax, and removed waxes, respectively. The boxplot
 569 summarizes median (center line), 75th and 25th percentile (box), and maximum and
 570 minimum corresponding to 1.5 times the interquartile range (whiskers), and possible
 571 outliers (diamonds) of measurements from 50 droplets for the pristine and molten leaf (and
 572 20 droplets after wax removal). Time-resolved signals for current, charge, and voltage are

573 given in Supplementary Fig. S12. The schematics on top of the graph illustrate the different
574 morphology of the waxes in the three cases reported: intact wax crystals in the pristine leaf,
575 molten waxes forming a flatter, continuous layer, and complete absence of epicuticular
576 waxes. c) Effect of the wax melting and wax removal on the water contact angle (N=5) of a
577 *C. antiquorum* leaf.

578

579

580 **Figure S13.** Current, charge, and voltage signals recorded for *C. antiquorum* of pristine
581 leaves, after changing the nanostructure of the epicuticular waxes by melting and after wax
582 removal by chloroform. Experiments were performed with DI water.

Fig. 7. Comparison of water droplet contact electrification on different plant species: fresh leaves of *N. nucifera*, *T. majus*, *C. antiquorum*, *H. helix*, *N. oleander* and *A. macrorrhiza*. Leaf-droplet interactions can be seen in Movies 2 and 3. The boxplot summarizes median (center line), 75th and 25th percentile (box), and maximum and minimum corresponding to 1.5 times the interquartile range (whiskers), and possible outliers (diamonds) of measurements from 50 droplets (except for *T. majus*, 20 droplets). The measurements have been performed after initially 3000 droplets have been dropped on the leaves. Leaf photographs and contact angle for each species are given.

Figure S15. Electric signals of liquid-solid contact electrification of artificial materials. a) Boxplot comparing the current signals produced by PET, silicone rubber, PTFE and FEP. b) Structure of the four artificial systems for measuring liquid-solid contact electrification on the top surface. c) Current, charge and voltage amplitudes as function of number of droplets (data points and error bars represent mean and average of 50 droplets each).

Discussion:

“Our results clearly confirm that living plant leaves are a platform that generates electrical signals upon contact with water droplets, either through contact electrification on the outer leaf or through pre-charged droplets landing on the leaf. In both cases, the charges received by the external leaf surface are electrostatically induced in the ion-conductive tissue.

When droplets are uncharged, cuticle contact electrification is significant cause of the electrical signal measured. Our results clearly show which factors of the leaf lead to higher or lower contact electrification upon droplet interaction. The effects are often deeply interconnected and mechanisms overlay on highly complex surfaces of the leaves. Yet, our results point to the

following behavior.

First, clearly, the epicuticular wax layer plays an essential role. The two features especially affecting leaf's liquid contact electrification are a) its nanostructure and b) its specific chemistry. The latter was anticipated for solid-solid contact electrification of leaves found by Kim et al.³³ Our results suggest that the wax presence and chemistry may play a more important role compared to its micro-/nanostructure as melting the waxes to achieve a flatter surface reduced the signals only about twice in *C. antiquorum*. However, removing the epicuticular waxes from the leaf reduced the signals tenfold. Moreover, the signals after wax-removal are reaching similar current, voltage and charge magnitudes to those obtained from plants that do not have a similarly dense wax layer. This suggests that the removal has clearly a more significant effect than just morphological changes in the wax layer.

Second, another important aspect is the superhydrophobicity. Results of the tests performed on the three superhydrophobic species showed that they generate higher signals compared with those obtained from the three tested hydrophilic species. However, superhydrophobicity/hydrophobicity alone is not sufficient to guarantee high (here, ~1-2 nA) leaf-droplet contact electrification signals: experiments with removed wax layers in *C. antiquorum* still showed hydrophobic behavior (contact angles 120°), but signals were low and similar to hydrophilic plants. This again shows that the presence of a dense, nanostructured wax layer is more important than hydrophobicity, although these two properties are often connected in natural conditions. However, there is another crucial feature of superhydrophobic surfaces, which is their ability for self-cleaning and complete removal of water from the surface. On hydrophilic plants, instead, water layers remain and may partially screen charges affecting signal formation and induction.^{8,9,16,44-46} Indeed, the contact time of the water droplet, the bouncing-off rates, and the remaining water films also play a role in liquid-solid contact electrification⁴⁷⁻⁴⁹. Moreover, although the droplet spreading area on the hydrophilic *A. macrorrhiza* and the superhydrophobic *C. antiquorum* was similar, it is expected that the water-surface contact area is higher on the hydrophilic leaf surface especially on the micro-/nanoscale^{50,51}. Increasing contact area is usually associated with higher leaf contact electrification and related signals^{3,52}. There may be several reasons why this was not observed in our case, for example the remaining water layers screening charges as mentioned above or the fact that efficient contact with few points on the surface is already sufficient to create high contact charges (one fundamental charge in about 100'000 surface atoms (~1000 nm²) can yield thousands of volts as highlighted by Lacks et al.⁵³). Here, again, the wax layers

nanostructure with multiple sharp edges which are transiently contacted by the droplet could provide such points/hot spots.

Next, to the leaf properties, also the properties of the droplet played an essential role in the leaf liquid-solid contact electrification. The role of pre-charged droplets, as occurring for example in thunderstorms is discussed later. The signals generated by uncharged water droplets on *C. antiquorum* leaves were strongly affected by the ion strengths and the pH following thereby trends also reported for artificial materials^{22,54,55}. Ion-rich solutions typically cause charge reduction by screening effects.^{55,56} The previous increase with the ion concentration that we observed in the *C. antiquorum* leaves below 1mM, seemed to be beneficial, e.g., an increasing droplet conductivity compared to deionized water as suggested in⁵⁵. Whereas then higher molarities caused a progressive decrease of the signals probably due to charge screening. Thus, superimposing effects may occur that do not always show a linear behavior and would need deeper investigation especially on complex leaf surfaces. Our results also show that the pH affects the signals amplitude. Whereas basic pH did not have a significant effect, at pH 3 (corresponding to an HCl concentration of 1mM) signals significantly reduced. The pH expectedly has an influence on the liquid-solid contact electrification^{44,55}. However, the effect of pH on leaves is more complex to determine. It was shown that exposure to pH 3 can significantly damage the epicuticular wax layer leading to a melted appearance as reported in⁵⁷. Thus, as we showed the strong effect of the wax layer on the signals when melting or removing the waxes, the signal reduction at low pH can be due to the damage of the wax layer. Yet, also in regards of occurrence of acidic rain in natural environments, a dedicated study of the complex effect of the pH in future would be interesting.”

2. The influence of different droplet motion states on solid-liquid triboelectricity is huge. The behavior of droplets on the surface interface shown in Figure 2, including collision, bounce, spreading, breaking, etc., has any specific effect on the generation of triboelectricity?

Thank you for this important question. We have performed additional experiments to track signal generation and droplet motion states by synchronizing high speed videos and registration of the electrical signals in high resolution. The results indicate that the signal is generated not immediately after contact but when the droplet is close to maximum expansion. The signal peak occurs when the droplet spreading is close to its maximum and the signal vanishes after the droplet broke and left the surface.

Materials and methods:

“Synchronized tracking of droplet motion and voltage signal generation:

To track droplet motion states and signal formation, synchronization of high-speed videos and voltage registration were done as follows: when a droplet hits the leaf, part of its kinetic energy

is transferred into the elastic deformation of the leaf blade. We positioned an electrode (1) under the leaf blade (fixed with dielectric double-sided tape to avoid electrical contact with the plant tissue) aligned with another electrode (2) fixed on a support in a distance of a few hundred micrometres from electrode (1). When a droplet hits a leaf, the two electrodes almost instantaneously touch due to the leaf deformation and close a circuit that generates a signal. This signal is recorded simultaneously with the triboelectric signals in the plant tissue using a multichannel oscilloscope. At the same time, we recorded the droplet interaction with a high-speed camera (Miro C110, Phantom High Speed, New Jersey, USA) at a framerate of ~ 1000 fps and observed a) droplet spreading and b) the moment when electrode 1 and 2 touch. The frame (when touch of electrodes 1 and 2 occurred) was used to synchronize video and electrical signals and could give real-time information on droplet deformation state and electrical signal."

Results:

"As previously shown in Fig. 2, the droplet behavior on the *C. antiquorum* leaf is complex. In order to investigate how the different droplet-leaf surface motion states correspond to the signal formation, we tracked the droplet motion in high-speed and simultaneously with the current signal (Fig. 3d). Time duration from droplet impact to its maximum spreading is only about 6 ms. The signal begins to develop shortly almost simultaneously with its maximum spreading and the current peak occurs after it, when the droplet already bursts and contracts/shrinks, reduces surface contact, and begins leaving the leaf. This suggests the mechanism depicted in Fig. 2e. When the droplet lands and spreads on the surface, contact electrification occurs and the droplet screens the generated charges. As soon as the droplet reduces surface contact, the charges become electrostatically induced into the inner tissue where the current is measured. On hydrophilic leaves the synchronization measurements were unsuccessful due to the too low signal amplitudes (~ 0.1 nA). Possible reasons for these lower signals are a) less charges form due to the different surface structure and b) charges are screened by remaining water films, as discussed later."

Fig. 3. [...] d) Time-domain synchronized analysis of droplet interaction and current signal formation in *C. antiquorum*. The images on the right are frames of high-speed camera recordings corresponding to the times of the signal formation. Movie 2 shows a high-speed video of a synchronized recording.

3. Figure 5a explores the influence of ion concentration on the electrical signal. Why does the electrical signal first increase and then decrease, and then increase and then decrease repeatedly with the increase of ion concentration? There should be a clear explanation for this.

We totally agree with you that this point needed further tests and clarification. We repeated the experiments taking into consideration that the signals may be more stable and comparable after multiple droplets (3000) have been exposed to the leaf (according to comment 3 of reviewer 1). The trend of the results was nevertheless still the same (initially rising signals with ion concentration, then decrease). We hence assume that there is a certain ion concentration at which the mechanism changes of how ions affect the electrical signals.

Interestingly, Zhang et al. (10.1016/j.nanoen.2020.105370) found on less complex artificial materials using a similar range of NaCl concentrations also that first an increase and then a decrease in output performance with increasing ion concentration may occur. They argued that contact electrification is affected by the ion concentration in two ways: when the concentration is below about 10^{-3} mol/L, an increase in ion concentration leads to an increase in conductivity in the droplet and enhances the signals, whereas when the concentration is above 10^{-3} mol/L, the high ion strengths screen charges leading to signal decrease. We assume that this effect may apply also in our case which is yet more challenging to analyse due to the leaf's surface complexity.

We added the following figure and text to the revised version.

Results:

“Increasing the ion concentration causes a behavior with apparently clear partitions: for low concentrations ($[\text{NaCl}] < 1\text{mM}$), increasing the ion concentration seems to enhance the signals compared to DI water, whereas for higher concentrations ($[\text{NaCl}] > 1\text{mM}$), the signal amplitudes are progressively suppressed. For a concentration of 1M NaCl, the signals even switch the polarity.”

Fig. 5. Effect of monovalent ion concentration and pH solutions on electric signals generated in *C. antiquorum*. a) Boxplot showing the effect of NaCl concentration on the generated current

amplitude. Each box represents 50 measurements recorded after previously 3000 droplets of the same solution have been dropped on the leaf.

Discussion:

“The signals generated by uncharged water droplets on *C. antiquorum* leaves were strongly affected by the ion strengths and the pH following thereby trends also reported for artificial materials^{22,54,55}. Ion-rich solutions typically cause charge reduction by screening effects.^{55,56}. The previous increase with the ion concentration that we observed in the *C. antiquorum* leaves below 1mM, seemed to be beneficial, e.g., an increasing droplet conductivity compared to deionized water as suggested in⁵⁵. Whereas then higher molarities caused a progressive decrease of the signals probably due to charge screening. Thus, superimposing effects may occur that do not always show a linear behavior and would need deeper investigation especially on complex leaf surfaces. Our results also show that the pH affects the signals amplitude. Whereas basic pH did not have a significant effect, at pH 3 (corresponding to an HCl concentration of 1mM) signals significantly reduced. The pH expectedly has an influence on the liquid-solid contact electrification^{44,55}. However, on leaves this is more complex. It was shown that exposure to pH 3 can significantly damage the epicuticular wax layer leading to a melted appearance as reported in⁵⁷. Thus, as we showed the strong effect of the wax layer on the signals when melting or removing the waxes, the signal reduction at low pH can be due to the damage of the wax layer. Yet, also in regards of occurrence of acidic rain in natural environments, a dedicated study of the complex effect of the pH in future would be interesting.”

4. More concentration gradients should be designed when exploring the effect of different pH on the output in Figure 5b.

We totally agree with you. Yet, measuring different pH solutions on leaves is very challenging. Acidic solutions are known to significantly damage the surface waxes of leaves (Hogrebe et al 1989, https://doi.org/10.1007/978-94-009-1023-2_2). Thus, it is extremely complex to distinguish the effect of the pH on contact electrification and the pH-caused damage of the waxes and its influence on the signals. Indeed, we showed how wax removal and small structural changes affect the signals. However, we hope to address these points in a dedicated study in the future as acidic rain is a phenomenon which frequently occurs.

We added the following in the revised manuscript.

Discussion:

“The pH expectedly has an influence on the liquid-solid contact electrification^{44,55}. However, on leaves this is more complex. It was shown that exposure to pH 3 can significantly damage the

epicuticular wax layer leading to a melted appearance as reported in ⁵⁷. Thus, as we showed the strong effect of the wax layer on the signals when melting or removing the waxes, the signal reduction at low pH can be due to the damage of the wax layer. Yet, also in regards of occurrence of acidic rain in natural environments, a dedicated study of the complex effect of the pH in future would be interesting. “

5. A phenomenon may be discovered quickly, but its basic understanding takes time. To better explain this plant-based triboelectricity, a charge transfer mechanism diagram should be supplemented.

We agree that there is still much to study to fully understand the charge transfer mechanism between raindrops and highly complex surfaces such as leaves. We performed additional experiments further elucidate the role of the structure and nature of the waxes on the electrical signals which provided valuable insights on the influence of nanostructure, surface wax distribution, hydrophobicity, species differences on the contact electrification of the leaves. Especially, the experiment you suggested on tracking current signal and droplet motion states confirmed a potential mechanism. We added a diagram showing the charge distribution on the cuticle and in the leaf tissue before, during, and after droplet interaction.

The following changes were made in the revised version.

Results:

“This suggests the mechanism depicted in Fig. 2e. When the droplet lands and spreads on the surface, contact electrification occurs and the droplet screens the generated charges. As soon as the droplet reduces surface contact, the charges become electrostatically induced into the inner tissue where the current is measured. On hydrophilic leaves the synchronization measurements were unsuccessful due to the too low signal amplitudes (~0.1 nA). Possible reasons for these lower signals are a) less charges form due to the different surface structure and b) charges are screened by remaining water films, as discussed later.”

Fig. 3. [...] e) Suggested mechanism for current signal formation based on liquid solid contact electrification and electrostatic induction of signals in the inner cellular tissue.

In summary, the present article does not contain in-depth scientific understanding enough for publication. In this regard, I cannot recommend this article for publication as it is. Instead, I recommend the authors make the experimental design more rigorous and focus on the study of its charge transfer mechanism, revise their manuscript significantly, and resubmit it to the journal if possible.

Thank you for your suggestion to improve the manuscript with revisions and additional experiments. We hope that the new set of experiments helped to better elucidate the complex mechanism leading contact electrification of the epicuticular waxes on the leaves.

Thank you again for the comments that have helped us to improve the manuscript.

21st Aug 22

Dear Dr Meder,

Your manuscript titled "Liquid-solid contact electrification in living plants" has now been seen again by the three referees, whose comments appear below. In light of their advice I am delighted to say that we are happy, in principle, to publish a suitably revised version in Communications Materials under the open access CC BY license (Creative Commons Attribution v4.0 International License).

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We hope to hear from you within two weeks; please let us know if the process may take longer.

Best regards,

Bilge Baytekin, PhD
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REVIEWERS' COMMENTS:

Reviewer #1 (Remarks to the Author):

The authors have answered the questions. It can be accepted.

Reviewer #2 (Remarks to the Author):

The authors have addressed all my comments and provided an improved manuscript. I therefore recommend publication to Communications Materials.

Reviewer #3 (Remarks to the Author):

I think the manuscript can be accepted in the current form.